

**BRIGHT
SPACE**

Funded by
the European Union

Horizon Europe
Grant Agreement
No. 101060075

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

This is the 6th newsletter of the BrightSpace project **WHERE YOU CAN:**

- Find out what BrightSpace is all about, & how to join our stakeholder community
- Read about the latest developments of the project & open access project results
- Know more about networking with other EU projects
- Get information on upcoming events

What is BrightSpace ?

BrightSpace is an EC funded 5-year Horizon Europe research and innovation action aiming to design effective and sustainable strategies to navigate the EU agriculture within a Safe and Just Operating Space.

[Read more »](#) | [Read our project flyer](#)

Dear BrightSpace Community,

Over the past months, since our 5th newsletter, BrightSpace has continued to deliver a strong set of results and modelling insights supporting informed debate on the future of European agriculture and food systems towards the Safe and Just Operating Space. We expanded our collection of *open-access discussion papers, peer-reviewed articles, datasets* and our first *policy brief*, and submitted second-period deliverables to the European Commission. These include the BrightSpace database and monitoring system prototype, reports on stakeholder-validated baselines, an enhanced BrightSpace Toolbox to assess SJOS aspects, promising technologies and consumption patterns, as well as impact assessments of planned EU policies.

Our outputs, covering topics such as smart farming governance, diet transitions, sustainable food systems and EU food loss and waste, reflect our commitment to accessible, policy-relevant knowledge. Strategic reflection continued through our governance and advisory processes. The *5th SPAB meeting* provided a valuable space for discussion on policy-relevant modelling and alignment with evolving policy needs. I also shared a *reflective stocktaking interview* reviewing the project's achievements and future directions, offering a personal perspective on our progress and ambitions.

Collaboration with other Horizon Europe projects deepened, particularly with LAMASUS and ACT4CAP27. A major outcome was the *Joint Perspective Paper on the future of EU agriculture*. Following a co-creation process launched in January, the paper was presented to DG AGRI in June and published on Zenodo in July, and has since been widely discussed at European and international events.

Our scientific and policy footprint continued to grow. *BrightSpace modelling insights were presented at European Commission events*, including the EC Cluster Meeting on Agricultural Policy and the SCAR Plenary. *Our participation in the EAAE Congress 2025* significantly raised the project's visibility and enabled valuable exchanges. Further contributions at the 18th IAMC Annual Meeting and ECOMOD 2025 strengthened links with global expert communities.

Capacity building remained a core focus. The CAPRI training session equipped participants with practical tools for evidence-based policy analysis, and preparations are underway for the 2026 LAMASUS – BrightSpace – TOOLS4CAP Summer School.

Stakeholder engagement remained central. The *2nd BrightSpace Stakeholder Retreat* in September, and as reflected in interviews with Work Package leads of WP5 & WP10, fostered in-depth exchange and kept the project closely connected to real-world needs.

Looking ahead to 2026, we look forward to our General Assembly in March in Cremona, which will provide an opportunity to take stock, plan next steps and strengthen partnerships.

We sincerely thank all partners, contributors and collaborators whose commitment and expertise drive BrightSpace forward.

As you read this newsletter, we invite you to explore the latest developments that have shaped BrightSpace this year. Thank you for being an integral part of our community.

Wishing you a joyful festive season and a prosperous New Year!

Best regards,

Marc Müller

BrightSpace Project Coordinator, on behalf of the BrightSpace team

Latest news from BrightSpace

ACT4CAP27 - BrightSpace - LAMASUS
 Joint Perspective Paper disseminated at
 the 43rd SCAR Plenary

[Read more »](#)

Apply Now: 2026 Summer School on
Advanced Modelling for Land-Use &
Policy Analysis

[Read more »](#)

New video: Interview with the project
coordinator

[Read more »](#)

Scientific and Policy Advisory Board
(SPAB) Meeting | 6 October 2025

[Read more »](#)

BrightSpace at EC Cluster Meeting on
Modelling Agricultural Policy | 25
September 2025

[Read more »](#)

BrightSpace Policy Brief is Out

[Read more »](#)

Stakeholder Engagement

BRIGHT SPACE
STAKEHOLDER EVENT
Stakeholder Retreat
We thank all participants for their contributions
23-24 September 2025

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101050075. Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

2nd BrightSpace Stakeholder Retreat | 23-24 September 2025

[Read more »](#)

BRIGHT SPACE
PROJECT INSIGHTS
NEW video: Interview with the leader of WP5
24 September 2025

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101050075. Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Interview with WP5 Lead Peter Witzke on Building the Project's Integrated Modelling Toolbox

[Read more »](#)

BRIGHT SPACE
PROJECT INSIGHTS
NEW video: Interview with the leader of WP10
24 September 2025

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101050075. Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Interview with WP10 Lead George Philippidis on the Future of EU Agricultural Transition Pathways

[Read more »](#)

BRIGHT SPACE WP11 Taskforce Meeting for planning the next Retreat
23 July 2025 | Online
BRIGHT SPACE STAKEHOLDER EVENT
2nd Stakeholder Retreat
The Crystall Ball – Futures of EU Agriculture
23 September 2025, 12:30 – 24 September 2025, 14:00 – Location: Martin's Klooster, Leuven, BE

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101050075. Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

WP11 taskforce meeting: preparing for the 2nd BrightSpace Retreat

[Read more »](#)

Further project Activities

BRIGHT SPACE WP12 Meeting | Online
1 October 2025

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101050075. Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

WP12 WP leaders' Meeting | 1 October 2025

[Read more »](#)

BRIGHT SPACE WP4 Meeting | Online
Evidence on EU and international policies
17 September 2025

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101050075. Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

WP4 Meeting | 17 September 2025

[Read more »](#)

Events of project communication & results dissemination

www.act4cap27.eu www.brightspace-project.eu www.lamasus.eu

ACT4CAP27 BRIGHT SPACE WE COOPERATE LAMASUS

Joint Perspective Paper presented at
FFA Market Outlook workshop | 7 November 2025

2025 Market outlook workshop Day 2

Funded by the European Union

Horizon Europe Grant Agreement Numbers: ACT4CAP27 101134874 | BrightSpace 101060075 | LAMASUS 101060423

Joint modelling insights for EU agri-food policy: Presentation by IIASA at the FFA 2025 Market Outlook Workshop

[Read more »](#)

18th IAMC Annual Meeting
11 - 13 November 2025

BRIGHT SPACE GLOBAL DISSEMINATION

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union. Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No 101060075. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

BrightSpace at the 18th IAMC Annual Meeting 2025

[Read more »](#)

ECOMOD2025
International Conference on
Economic Modeling and Data Science

BRIGHT SPACE DISSEMINATION

3-5 September 2025
BADEN-WÜRTTEMBERG COOPERATIVE STATE UNIVERSITY
STUTTGART, GERMANY

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union. Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No 101060075. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

BrightSpace at EcoMod2025 Conference

[Read more »](#)

www.act4cap27.eu www.brightspace-project.eu www.lamasus.eu

ACT4CAP27 BRIGHT SPACE WE COOPERATE LAMASUS

Joint Perspective Paper presented at
35th ÖGA Conference | 18 September 2025

Sustainable agricultural sector
A key component of
EU economic prosperity and security

Funded by the European Union

Horizon Europe Grant Agreement Numbers: ACT4CAP27 101134874 | BrightSpace 101060075 | LAMASUS 101060423

Joint perspective paper presented at Austrian Society of Agricultural Economics Annual Conference

[Read more »](#)

50eaae 2025
EAAE CELEBRATING ITS 50TH ANNIVERSARY

XVIII EAAE Congress
26-29 August 2025 Bonn, DE

BRIGHT SPACE DISSEMINATION

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union. Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No 101060075. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

BrightSpace at EAAE 2025- Part 2: Advancing Agricultural Economics in Bonn

[Read more »](#)

50eaae 2025
EAAE CELEBRATING ITS 50TH ANNIVERSARY

XVIII EAAE Congress
26-29 August 2025 Bonn, DE

BRIGHT SPACE DISSEMINATION

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union. Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No 101060075. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

BrightSpace at EAAE 2025- Part 1: Advancing Agricultural Economics in Bonn

[Read more »](#)

BrightSpace reports & Open Access publications

OXFORD ACADEMIC
Open
A Journal of Agricultural, Climata, Environmental, Food, Resource, and Rural Development Economics

EAAEP Foundation
European Agricultural and Applied Economics Publications Foundation

BRIGHT SPACE
Open Access Results

JOURNAL ARTICLE | ACCEPTED MANUSCRIPT
Towards a Safe and Just Operating Space for European Agriculture
Marc Müller, Hervé Guyomard, Hans van Meijl, Cécile Détang-Dessendre, Elisa Bazzani, Michiel van Dijk, Paolo Sckokai, Elke Stehfest, Christoph Krüger, Lukáš Čechura, Beyhan de Jong, Robert M'Barek
Q Open, qoaf026, <https://doi.org/10.1093/qopen/qoaf026>
Published: 25 September 2025

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union. Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No 101000075. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The Lancet Planetary Health
Volume 9, Issue 10, October 2025, 101327

ISSN: 2352-3409

BRIGHT SPACE
Open Access Results

Articles
Exploring environmental and distributional impacts of different transition pathways for healthier and sustainable diets: an economic modelling study Open access
Marjolke Kujper PhD^{1,2,3,4}, Thijs de Lange MSc^{5,6}, Willem-Jan van Zeist PhD⁷, Prof Frans van Meijl PhD^{1,8}
Available online 3 November 2025, Version of Record 3 November 2025.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanph.2025.101327>

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union. Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No 101000075. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

zenodo
BrightSpace Horizon Europe project
Part of EU Open Research Repository

Published October 30, 2025 | Version v1

BRIGHT SPACE
Open Access Results

EU Food Loss and Waste (FLW) Panel Data (2003–2022): Estimates and Drivers.
Fernan Pérez, Hugo (Researcher)¹, Philippidis, George (Researcher)²
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17483953](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17483953)

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union. Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No 101000075. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Food Policy
Volume 136, October 2025, 102955

ISSN: 0306-9192

BRIGHT SPACE
Open Access Results

The role of pesticides and fertilizers in Czech cereal output and TFP growth: A flexible production function with endogenous inputs Open access
Lukáš Čechura^{1,2*}, Subal C. Kumbhakar^{3,4}, Zdenka Žáková Kroupová^{5,6}
Received 9 September 2024, Revised 22 August 2025, Accepted 28 August 2025, Available online 25 September 2025, Version of Record 25 September 2025.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2025.102955>

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union. Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No 101000075. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

BRIGHT SPACE
DISSEMINATION
Open Access Results

Read this working paper on our Zenodo Community page
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17607992](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17607992)

BRIGHT SPACE

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Steering Smart Farming Technology Adoption toward a Safe and Just Operating Space
Discussion paper
Authors: Lutz Adewale (ERC), Mikael Finger, Mathis Thomas, Mik Kumbhakar, Hugo Steiner (ERDF)

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union. Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No 101000075. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

On 30 October 2025 we marked the

3 years anniversary of **BRIGHT SPACE**

with submitting **6 deliverables** to the European Commission

BrightSpace is funded by the European Union.

For the full list of available publications visit our website's Resources page:
<https://brightspace-project.eu/resources/>

Networking & Cooperation with Horizon Europe Projects

<https://www.brightspace-project.eu/> | <https://www.genebecon.eu/> | <https://www.ration-erp.eu/>

BRIGHT SPACE **GeneBEcon** **RATION**

03/11/2025 Inter-project meeting online

BrightSpace Grant Agreement Nr. 101000075
GeneBEcon Grant Agreement Nr. 1010051015
RATION Grant Agreement Nr. 1010084163

Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Funded by the European Union

Sustainable agricultural sector:
A key component of EU economic prosperity and security
An economic modellers' perspective

A joint paper by the Horizon Europe projects

ACT4CAP²⁷ BRIGHT SPACE LAMASUS

Horizon Europe Grant Agreement Numbers: ACT4CAP27 101134974 | BrightSpace 101000075 | LAMASUS 101060423
Views are of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Further highlights from our fellow projects

➔ LAMASUS at EU events:

➔ [FADN2025 | Forum for the future of Agriculture](#)

➔ [Policy Brief: Maximizing CAP Impact](#)

➔ [Annual meeting 21-22/10/2025](#)

➔ [LAMASUS at EAAE2025 conference](#)

➔ [LAMASUS resources](#)

➔ Tools: [LAMASUS Modelling Portal](#) |

[LUM Driver Database](#) | [Knowledgebase](#)

➔ [2nd Stakeholder Meeting](#)
[6/11/2025 – Read Press Release](#)

➔ [ACT4CAP27 at EAAE Congress](#)
[26-29/8/2025, Bonn DE](#)

➔ [ACT4CAP27 policy brief](#)

➔ [Join the ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder Platform](#)

GeneBEcon project closed on 31/08/2025

[Read more on CORDIS Results »](#)

➔ [GeneBEcon final Symposium](#)
[2/7/2025, Brussels BE](#)

➔ [GeneBEcon resources: public deliverables](#)
[& publications](#)

➔ [3rd annual meeting, Heraklion, Crete](#)
[29/10/2025](#)

➔ [RATION launches new application](#)

➔ [5th Newsletter 07/2025](#)

➔ [2nd Policy Brief 04/2025](#)

➔ [RATION deliverables](#)

Upcoming events

- ➔ EU Agri-Food Days, 15-17 December 2025, Brussels, BE
- ➔ BrightSpace annual meeting, 10-12 March 2026, Cremona, IT
- ➔ FFA Conference, 14 April 2026, Brussels, BE
- ➔ 100th AES Conference, 23-25 April 2026, Oxford, UK
- ➔ 54th SGA Conference, 7-8 May 2026, Zollikofen, CH
- ➔ LAMASUS / BrightSpace / Tools4CAP Summer School, 8-12 June 2026, Laxenburg, AT
- ➔ 11th EAAE PhD Workshop, 17-19 June 2026, Évora, PT
- ➔ 16th IFSA Conference, 29 June – 3 July 2026, Montpellier, FR
- ➔ 30th ICABR Conference 7-10 July 2026, Ravello, IT
- ➔ EcoMod2026 Conference, 8-10 July 2026, Luxemburg

**BRIGHT
SPACE**

More information will be sent in our next BrightSpace newsletter scheduled for spring 2026.

Thank you for signing up to the [BrightSpace newsletters](#).

Further information can be found on the BrightSpace project homepage:

www.brightspace-project.eu | www.brightspace-horizon.eu

FOLLOW US ON OUR CHANNELS

PARTNERS

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Horizon Europe **Grant Agreement No 101060075**. Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

